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Proposed Research Model on Social Responsibility and Green Marketing Strategy in Vietnam Agricultural Eco-Tourism Industry

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Abstract:

The objective of the article is to review related studies, analyze the current situation and find theoretical gaps. From there, we propose a research model to assess the impact of social responsibility and green marketing strategies on the performance of Vietnamese agro-ecological tourism enterprises.

Keywords: Corporate social responsibility, green marketing strategy, Vietnam

1. Introduction

The development of the tourism industry in general and travel tourism has promoted the development of many other economic sectors such as: commerce (customer shopping), industry (through energy consumption, building materials, etc.). Construction of technical facilities for tourism, means of transport (airlines, roads, waterways, railways), agriculture (supply of food, food...); construction (hotels, houses). restaurants, amusement parks, etc.), banking (foreign currency exchange), post and telecommunications (telephone services, information transmission) and in many provinces and cities, tourism has affirmed its position as an important economic sector. important contribution to the development of many localities of the country.

The development of tourism and travel activities has created more jobs for the society, especially in rural tourism destinations, community-based tourism in remote areas. According to the 2018 report of the WTTC (World Travel and Tourism Council) on the socio-economic impacts of tourism and travel, in 2017, the labor force in Vietnam's tourism industry was about 2.5 million people, ranking second. 7 in the world (first is China with 28.5 million workers) and 2nd in ASEAN (Indonesia ranks first with 4.5 million workers). In addition, the development of tourism contributes to poverty reduction and economic restructuring.

Tourism has become a key economic sector in economic development strategies in many countries due to its great contributions to socio-economics. For developing economies, tourism can play an important role in economic, poverty reduction, promotion of social progress (Blanke and Chiesa, 2011).

In addition, research on the impact of social responsibility on performance results has been studied by many domestic and foreign authors, but the results are still conflicting. Especially, the combination of green marketing strategy research variables in this relationship is limited, especially in the tourism and travel industry; there are very few studies on this topic.

2. Research overview

2.1. Corporate social responsibility

Stakeholders are the main target audience of social responsibility and therefore they are the people that companies need to care to please (Pérez and Bosque, 2014). In the service industry, tourism is considered a complex and dynamic industry, involving many subjects. The goals of these actors are different, so it is difficult to balance the interests of all stakeholders. Therefore, it is important to reduce conflicts through building effective relationships between stakeholders. Previous study authors have used stakeholder theory to address

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this. Pearce et al (1998) argue that the identification of stakeholders in the tourism industry is increasingly interested. A plan without the support of stakeholders will be very difficult to implement and achieve the goal.

Newsome et al. (2002) argue that the stakeholders in the tourism industry include directly affected tourists and indirectly affected local communities. In addition, people such as government offices, tourism program developers and operators are also considered stakeholders. From that point of view, Lewis and Newsome (2003) focused on the analysis of stakeholders in their research, namely visitors, local communities, tour operators, and regional tourism offices.

Murphy and Murphy (2004) identify four distinct groups in the tourism industry: customers; industry; citizen; government. Hardy and Beeton (2001) when researching on the sustainable development of the tourism industry, said that there are four related subjects: people at that tourist destination; traveler; travel agency and natural environment.

According to Byrd (2007), stakeholders are citizens, tourists, government, travel agencies and NGOs. Or like Wei and Ruirui (2013), there are four main groups involved, namely local government, tour operators, locals and tourists when researching sustainable tourism development in China.

Thus the stakeholders may differ in different cases, depending on the specific situations, however the subjects appearing in most of the above studies are tourists, travel agencies, local government and local people. In summary, the study inherits the concept of social responsibility of Misha and Saura (2010) and Hasan et al. (2018) when considering based on stakeholders, and at the same time inherits Wei and Ruirui (2013) and ideas expert opinion when identifying stakeholders in the tourism industry in Vietnam. Corporate social responsibility in the tourism industry is the responsibility of the travel business to its stakeholders, tourists, tour operators, local authorities and local people. This is the content of the concept of corporate social responsibility in the tourism industry used in this study.

2.2. Green marketing strategy

For the service industry, green marketing is also gradually proving its effectiveness. Services are often considered as an intangible, non-storable process, however, in reality, the service delivery process is still using tangible products, using resources and generating waste. therefore, the service sector still has huge impacts on the environment (Meler and Ham, 2012). Especially the tourism service industry, which contributes greatly to the GDP of the country but it is also using resources and creating waste. Applying a green marketing strategy to the tourism industry also receives a lot of attention from researchers and businesses when they realize that they can control costs, increase profits, and build customer loyalty. Meler and Ham, 2012). Specifically, the benefits of green marketing for tourism businesses such as:

- Cut costs: The process of tourism businesses operating towards the environment will help the use of resources more efficiently, through which there will be changes in the cost model.
- Differentiation from competitors: By providing new tourism products in the market or creating added value for existing products, businesses can find new market segments, improve customer loyalty and increase profits, improve position in the market.
- New vitality of a business: A business can use the environmental performance process as an opportunity to restore its product and position.

According to Meler and Ham (2012), the green marketing strategy in the tourism industry consists of key elements such as (1) creating and developing an environmentally friendly market segment; (2) based on the latest environmental standards and requirements to have a systematic monitoring, evaluation and inspection of all market activities and tourism product lines; (3) redefining the quality of tourism products; (4) redefining

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marketing and communication strategies with the market and the general public; with environmental groups and organizations, with countries; (5) create new environmental standards and launch new environmental initiatives; (6) product labels must be associated with environmental factors.

The content of green marketing strategy in the service industry in general and the tourism industry in particular

According to Pomeroy and Johnson (2018), the green marketing conceptual framework (4Ps) used for tangible products can also be used for services, however, this approach is not enough for marketers to improve business results. corporate sustainability.

According to Booms and Bitner (1981), Goi (2009), Arseculeratne and Yazdanifard (2014), Eneizen (2016), the green marketing mix in the service sector should include 7Ps and each element of the green marketing mix must convey be environmentally friendly (Arseculeratne and Yazdanifard, 2014). Therefore, the study will combine the research of Leonidou et al. (2013), Fraj et al. (2012), Dief and Font (2010) to consider and measure green marketing strategies with the 7Ps model (products, green products, green prices, green distribution, green promotion, green people, green physical conditions, green processes) in a way that is responsible for the environment and stakeholders.

2.3. Corporate reputation

Corporate reputation reflects stakeholders' perceptions of the organization. This perception is formed over time based on the experiences of different stakeholders and from corporate communications. Taghian et al. (2015), when it comes to corporate reputation, it is advisable to focus on management aspects because it will comprehensively consider the perspectives of stakeholders. Each stakeholder has different expectations and attitudes, so their understanding and perception of business operations will also be different. Only managers who contact all stakeholders can assess the importance of stakeholders, thereby forming the right strategy. Therefore, in this study agreeing with Taghian et al. (2015), corporate reputation is measured by managers' perception of the opinions of all stakeholders, not considering on the opinion of a particular stakeholder. At the same time, the study also inherits the scale from Taghian et al (2015) to build a scale for this research concept.

2.4. Business results

Business results is a complex concept, as shown in Section 2.5, the study will continue to study business results associated with stakeholders like Freeman's concept.

Freeman (1984) defines business performance as the total value created by the business through its activities, which is the sum of the utilities generated for each legitimate stakeholder of the business.

At the same time, the study inherits the studies of Bou-llusar et al. (2009), Fraj et al (2012) to build a scale for the business outcome factor with stakeholders.

2.5. Supply chain efficiency

Supply chain performance is very often considered when compared to company performance. There we have financial and non-financial performance measures, though. One model used to measure financial performance at the supply chain level is governance value analysis (GVA), proposed by Gosh and John (Hammervoll, 2009). It takes into account two elements of value created: relational value (shared profit) and agent value (shared profit). Based on these two values, the authors attempt to prove the relationship between the two firms, mainly using the theory of transaction cost economics (TCE). Several other studies have extended the value chain creation measurement from the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) to the Supply Chain Operations Reference Model (SCOR) (Barber, 2008). The truth is that there is no universally accepted methodology for measuring value creation in the supply chain, all they suggest is that performance cannot be measured with just one key performance indicator from a side of the business that must use more than one performance indicator. If we consider the

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negative outcomes that a supply chain can produce, such as a bad reputation, bad image for customers, loss of trust from customers and other organizations - the situation became more and more confused. However, perhaps an overall supply chain performance score would include positive and negative influences. A generally accepted issue is the fact that performance must be measured at the corporate level and not for each part of the supply chain. This acceptance ensures that supply chain management can be seen as one of the possible causes of future overall supply performance.

3. Proposed research model

The theory of social responsibility and the theory of green marketing is the basis to support the point, when businesses want to increase business results, it is necessary to have the right strategies and show their responsibility throughout the process. business execution. In recent years, many authors have conducted exploratory as well as empirical research to understand the relationship between green marketing and business performance (eg Menon and Menon, 1997; Baker and Sinkula, 2005a; Charter et al., 2002; Ginsberg and Bloom, 2004), the relationship between social responsibility and business performance (eg, Maignan et al., 1999; Lindgreen et al. (2009); Margolis and Waslsh (e.g., Maignan et al., 1999; Lindgreen et al. (2009); Margolis and Waslsh). 2003); Qu (2009); Malik (2015); Taghian et al (2015), Hoang, 2015), the relationship between social responsibility and green marketing (eg Polonsky, 1996; Lindgreen et al., 2009). In particular, some authors have also found that corporate reputation is a concept affected by green marketing strategy (eg Lawrence, 1991, Porter and Van der Linde, 1995, Vaccaro, 2009), by responsibility (e.g. Bertels and Peloza, 2008; Lai et al., 2010; Lii and Lee, 2012; Taghian et al., 2015), while corporate reputation also increases business performance (eg. as Neville et al., 2005; Lai et al., 2010; Taghian et al., 2015). The relationship between these concepts is shown in detail as follows:

Figure 1. Research model of the topic

3.1. The relationship between corporate social responsibility and corporate reputation

Corporate reputation will help shape consumer attitudes and perceptions about that business (Fombrun and Shanley, 1990), which in turn will boost consumer buying motivation and help position the brand (Neville et al. associates, 2005). Many studies (Lai et al., 2010; Lii and Lee, 2012) have shown that consumer buying behavior is greatly influenced by corporate reputation. Therefore, businesses need to build a reputation for themselves through many activities, in which corporate activities related to social responsibility have the ability to greatly affect business reputation (Boyd et al. , 2010; Lii and Lee, 2012).

Carroll and Shabana (2010) find that, in order to increase consumer awareness, improving corporate image, reputation and social responsibility is a proposed strategic tool to do this. Bertels and Peloza (2008); Lai et al. (2010) also argue that social responsibility activities have an impact on the company's reputation. And Lii and

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Lee (2012) find that corporate social activities play an important role in shaping corporate reputation in the perception of stakeholders. Research by Taghian et al (2015) has also found that socially responsible activities will increase corporate reputation, help businesses better position themselves, and enhance competitive advantages. From the above arguments, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Corporate social responsibility has a positive impact on corporate reputation

3.2. The relationship between green marketing strategy and corporate reputation

Green marketing will lead to brand loyalty (Karna and Juslin, 2003; Arseculeratne and Yazdanifard, 2014). Green products will bring a new awareness of consumers about the environment. Businesses operating for the environment will position their reputation in the hearts of consumers, increasing their visibility among countless businesses in the market. When businesses have created brand loyalty from customers, it will reduce product price sensitivity. If the price of green products is more expensive, consumers will accept it because they trust the reputation of the business and believe that the product is good for health as well as the environment.

Research by Lawrence (1991); Porter and Van der Linde (1995) said that by implementing green marketing, it will bring a better image, brand, and reputation for the business. And many research articles (such as Miles and Covin, 2000; Menon and Menon, 1997; Kolk, 2003; DiFrangia, 2008) compiled in Vaccaro's study (2009) also suggest that green marketing will help businesses increase its reputation. From there, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Green marketing strategy has a positive impact on corporate reputation

3.3. The relationship between green marketing strategy and business results

Implementing green marketing brings core benefits to businesses. If an enterprise applies a green production process, it will cut costs in the process of discharge, reduce resource use, save energy, which helps them reduce production costs and increase profits. Baker and Sinkula, 2005a).

Research by Menon and Menon (1997) also confirms that a successful green marketing strategy will increase revenue, profit and market share. Strategies related to the environment will increase operational efficiency, develop new technologies, gain competitive advantage and increase profits (Porter and Van der Linde, 1995). Research by Charter et al (2002); Ginsberg and Bloom (2004); Kassaye (2001) all said that when businesses implement green marketing, they will help consumers access green products and when consumers accept to pay high prices to buy green products, businesses will increase revenue. and the profit. From there, the research hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Green marketing strategy has a positive impact on business results

3.4. The relationship between corporate social responsibility and business results

The relationship between social responsibility and business performance is also found in many previous studies. Hoang's research (2015) has found many studies that say there is a negative relationship between social responsibility and business performance (Vance, 1975; Ullman, 1985) or no relationship with each other (Alexander et al. Buchholz, 1978; Abbott and Monsen, 1979; Aupperle et al., 1985). However, there are also many authors who have studied to find a positive relationship between social responsibility and business performance such as Maignan et al (1999); Lindgreen et al (2009); Margolis et al (2009); Qu (2009); Malik (2015); Taghian et al (2015). Therefore, this study proposes the hypothesis:

H4: Corporate social responsibility has a positive impact on business results

3.5. The relationship between corporate reputation and business results

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When businesses build a reputation, they also position their image in the perception of consumers and stakeholders (Neville et al., 2005). This is the motivation that customers will choose them when deciding to consume. Neville et al (2005) have shown that there is a link between corporate reputation and business performance. Social responsibility activities will affect the business's reputation and lead to an increase in business results of the business (Lai et al., 2010). Taghian et al. (2015) found that corporate reputation had an impact on market share but had no direct impact on profitability. From here, the author proposes the hypothesis:

H5a: Corporate reputation has a positive effect on business results

H5b: Corporate reputation has a positive effect on supply chain efficiency

3.6. The relationship between green marketing strategy and supply chain efficiency

Many authors believe that the perception of stakeholders is that the pressure on managers to make commitments to protect the environment (Henriques and Sadorsky, 1999; Buysse and Verbeke, 2003). From there, it shows a relationship between the level of managers' awareness of social responsibility and the level of green marketing implementation. Currently, there are very few studies that address this influence (Rivera-Camino, 2007), only a few authors mention the position of stakeholders that influence the overall strategy such as Freeman (Rivera-Camino, 2007). 1984) pointed out that it is necessary to study from the perspective of stakeholders because it is a way of managing behavior to meet stakeholder expectations. Similarly, Roberts and King (1989) also said that stakeholders have an influence on the orientation and strategy formulation of the enterprise, this is also mentioned in the study of Polonsky (1996). And Lindgreen et al. (2009) argue that when implementing marketing activities, it is related to the whole supply chain and improves supply chain efficiency. Therefore, the author proposes the hypothesis:

H6: Does green marketing strategy have a positive impact on supply chain efficiency?

4. Conclusion

Today, the concept of "Responsible Tourism" is not a new type of tourism, but has a very important meaning.

The nature of this type of tourism contains the characteristics of sustainable tourism development, but it is universal, more oriented and even regulates all other types of tourism in order to target develop the tourism industry to achieve harmony, bring equal benefits to all actors involved in the tourism development process. At the same time, it contributes significantly in supporting the creation of a healthy environment for socio-economic benefits.

Responsible tourism includes several basic features: Minimization of negative economic, social and environmental impacts; bring more benefits to local people and increase income for destination communities, improve working conditions and create more job opportunities for the tourism industry; encourage people to participate in decision-making on issues that may affect their livelihood opportunities; actively contribute to the conservation of natural and cultural heritages, maintaining diversity; bring many interesting experiences to tourists through communication with the local community, thereby helping them to deepen their understanding of the local culture, society and environment; creating conditions for people to have easier access to tourism services; enhance mutual respect and understanding between tourists and destination communities, and build people's confidence and pride in tourist destinations.

References

- i Arseculeratne, D. and R. Yazdanifard, 2014. *How Green Marketing Can Create a Sustainable Competitive Advantage for a Business. International Business Research*, 7: 130-137.
- ii Aupperle K., Carroll A., Hatfield J., 1985. *An Empirical Examination of the Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility and Profitability. Academy of Management Journal*, 28:446- 463.

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- iii Bai, X., & J. Chang, 2015. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Firm Performance: The Mediating Role of Marketing Competence and the Moderating Role of Market eNvironment*. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 32:505-530.
- iv Bansal, P. and K. Roth, 2000. *Why Companies Go Green: a Model of Ecological Responsiveness*. *Academy of Management Journal*, 43:717-36.
- v Baker, W.E., & J.M. Sinkula, 2005a. *Environmental Marketing Strategy and Firm Performance: Effects on New Product Performance and Market Share*. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 33: 461–475.
- vi Barrett, S., 1991. *Environmental Regulations for Competitive Advantage*. *Business Strategy Review* 2:1–15.
- vii Bartlett, E. and N. Howard, 2000. *Informing the Decision Makers on the Cost and Value of Green Building*. *Building Research and Information*, 28:315-324.
- viii Berman, S. L., A. C. Wicks, S. Kotha and T. M. Jones, 1999. *Does Stakeholder Orientation Matter? The Relationship between Stakeholder Management Models and Firm Financial Performance*. *Academy of Management Journal*, 42:488-506.
- ix Bertels, S. and J. Pelozo, 2008. *Running Just to Stand Still? Managing CSR Reputation in An Era of Ratcheting Expectations*. *Corporate Reputation Review*, 11:56-72.
- x Berry, L.L., 1983. *Relationship Marketing of Services – Growing Interest, Emerging Perspective*. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 23:236-45.
- xi Blanke, J., T. Chiesa, 2011. *The Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index 2011: Assessing Industry Drivers in the Wake of the Crisis*. *The Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Report 2011*, World Economic Forum, 3-34.
- xii Booms, B.H, M.J. Bitner, 1981. *Marketing Strategies and Organization Structures for Service Firms*. In *Advance in Marketing of Services*. Donnelly, J.H., George, W.R., Eds.; American Marketing Association: Chicago, IL, USA.
- xiii Bonoma, T.V. and B. H. Clark, 1988. *Marketing Performance Assessment*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.
- xiv Borden, N.H., 1964. *The Concept of the Marketing Mix*. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 4:2-7.
- xv Borin, N., J. Mullikin and R. Krishanan, 2013. *An Analysis of Consumer Reaction to Green Strategies*. *Journal of Production and Brand Management*, 22:118-128.
- xvi Bowen, H.R., 1953. *Social Responsibilities of the Businessman*. New York: Harper & Row.
- xvii Bou-Llusar, J.C., A.B. Escrig-Tena, V. Roca-Puig, I. Beltra'n-Marti'n, 2009. *An empirical assessment of the EFQM Excellence Model: Evaluation as a TQM framework relative to the MBNQA Model*. *Journal of Operations Management*, 27:1–22.
- xviii Boyd, B.K., D.D. Bergh and D.J. Jr. Ketchen, 2010. *Reconsidering the Reputation-Performance Relationship: a Resource-Based View*. *Journal of Management*, 36:588-609.
- xix Bridges, C. M. and W.B. Wilhelm, 2008. *Going Beyond Green: The "Why and how" of Integrating Sustainability into the Marketing Curriculum*. *Journal of Marketing Education*, 30:33-46.